

Studies in the Synthesis of Quinoline Derivatives. Part V¹. Synthesis of 1, 2-bis (2-chloro-4-quinolyl) ethane Derivatives

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4-Bromomethylcarbostyryl (Ia) on treatment with phosphorus oxychloride gave 4-chloromethyl-2-chloroquinoline (Ib) which with alcoholic potassium cyanide afforded 1-cyano-1,2-bis(2-chloro-4-quinolyl)ethane (IIb). This was also prepared from (Ia) by first reacting it with potassium cyanide to give 1-cyano-1,2-bis(2-hydroxy-4-quinolyl)ethane (IIa) followed by treatment with phosphorus oxychloride. Again (IIb) on hydrolysis with 70% sulphuric acid gave 1,2-bis(2-chloro-4-quinolyl)ethane. This was also prepared from (IIa) by treatment of 70% sulphuric acid followed by phosphorus oxychloride.

The present work was undertaken in continuation of the study of the reactivity of 4-bromomethyl carbostyryl derivatives described earlier^{2,3}. 4-Bromomethylcarbostyryl (Ia) when reacted with potassium cyanide in ethyl alcohol gave 1-cyano-1,2-bis(2-hydroxy-4-quinolyl)ethane (IIa) instead of 4-cyanomethylcarbostyryl (Ic). This is a novel observation in this series. They are converted into their 2-chloro derivatives by treatment with phosphorus oxychloride. Thus (IIa) gave 1-cyano-1,2-bis(2-chloro-4-quinolyl)ethane (IIb). The structure (IIb) was assigned on the basis of analytical data and its IR spectrum (nujol) showed a characteristic nitrile band at 2240 cm⁻¹. Its NMR spectrum (60 MHz : CDCl₃) showed the presence of aromatic, methine and methylene protons as follows :

Shift (δ)	Coupling constant J (C/Sec)	Signals	Assignment
7.5 to 8.5	—	Multiplet	10 H (Aromatic)
5.1	8	Triplet	1 H
4.2	8	Doublet	2 H

(IIb) was also obtained by first treating 4-bromomethylcarbostyryl with phosphorus oxychloride which gave 4-chloromethyl-2-chloroquinoline (Ib) and not 4-bromomethyl-2-chloroquinoline (Id). (Ib) on treatment with potassium cyanide gave (IIb). Again 1-cyano-1,2-bis(2-hydroxy-4-quinolyl)ethane (IIa), on hydrolysis with 70% sulphuric acid, was degraded to 1,2-bis(2-hydroxy-4-quinolyl)ethane (IIc) which was converted into corresponding 2-chloro derivative (IIId) by treatment with phosphorus oxychloride. This was also obtained when (IIb) was subjected to hydrolysis with 70% sulphuric acid.

Using these procedures, the following (i) 2-chloro-4-chloromethylquinoline derivatives, (ii) 1-cyano-1,2-bis (2-hydroxy-4-quinolyl)ethane derivatives, (iii) 1-cyano-1,2-bis(2-chloro-4-quinolyl)ethane derivatives and (iv) 1,2-bis(2-chloro-4-quinolyl)ethane derivatives have been

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prepared from 8-methyl-4-bromomethylcarbostyryl, 6-chloro-4-bromomethylcarbostyryl and 6-bromo-4-bromomethylcarbostyryl.

I	R ₁	R ₂	X	Y	II	R ₁	R ₂	X	Y
a	H	H	Br	OH	a	H	H	CN	OH
b	H	H	Cl	Cl	b	H	H	CN	Cl
c	H	H	CN	OH	c	H	H	H	OH
d	H	H	Br	Cl	d	H	H	H	Cl

EXPERIMENTAL

4-Chloromethyl-2-chloroquinoline derivatives : 4-Bromomethylcarbostyryl (Ia) derivative (5 g.) was treated with phosphorus oxychloride (15 ml.) and heated in an oil bath at 110–20° for 2 hrs. It was poured over ice water with stirring and the solution was neutralised with sodium hydroxide solution. The separated product (Table I) was filtered and crystallised from benzene petroleum ether mixture (1 : 1). Yield 55–60%.

TABLE I

4-Chloromethyl-2-chloroquinoline derivatives

No.	Substituent in 4-chloromethyl-2-chloroquinoline	M.P. °C	Molecular formula	Analysis %			
				required		found	
				N	Cl	N	Cl
1.	Unsubstituted	99	C ₁₀ H ₇ NCl ₂	6.60	33.49	6.53	33.10
2.	8-methyl	80	C ₁₁ H ₇ NCl ₂	6.19	31.42	5.95	31.78
3.	6-chloro	116	C ₁₀ H ₆ NCl ₃	5.68	45.20	5.45	42.74
4.	6-bromo	124	C ₁₀ H ₆ NBrCl ₂	4.82	—	4.71	—

C = 41.24; H = 2.06 C = 40.91; H = 2.06

1-Cyano-1,2-bis(2-chloro-4-quinolyl)ethane derivatives : The above chloromethyl derivative (1 g.) in alcohol (10 ml.) was treated with potassium cyanide (0.5 g. in 1 ml. water) and refluxed on a steam bath for 3 hrs. On cooling the product which separated (Table II) was crystallised from benzene or benzene-petroleum ether mixture (1 : 1). Yield 50–55%.

TABLE II

1-Cyano-1,2-bis(2-chloro-4-quinolyl)ethane derivatives

No.	Substituent in 1-cyano-1,2-bis- (2-chloro-4- quinolyl)ethane	M.P. °C	Molecular formula	Analysis %					
				required			found		
				C	H	N	C	H	N
1.	Unsubstituted	211	C ₂₁ H ₁₃ N ₃ Cl ₂	66.66	3.44	11.11	67.00	3.23	11.00
2.	8-methyl	178	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ N ₃ Cl ₂	67.98	4.18	10.34	68.42	4.12	10.29
3.	6-chloro	274	C ₂₁ H ₁₁ N ₃ Cl ₄	56.38	2.46	9.39	56.08	2.63	9.47
4.	6-bromo	272	C ₂₁ H ₁₁ N ₃ Cl ₂ Br ₂	47.01	2.05	7.84	47.21	2.10	8.14

1-Cyano-1,2-bis(2-hydroxy-4-quinolyl)ethane derivatives: 4-Bromomethylcarbostyryl (Ia) derivative (1 g.) in alcohol (40 ml.) was treated with potassium cyanide (0.5 g. in 2 ml. water) on a steam bath for 3 hrs. On cooling the separated product (Table III) was filtered and crystallised from glacial acetic acid. Yield 55–60%.

TABLE III

1-Cyano-1,2-bis(2-hydroxy-4-quinolyl)ethane derivatives

No.	Substituent in 1-cyano-1,2-bis (2-hydroxy-4- quinolyl)ethane	M.P. °C	Molecular formula	Analysis %					
				required			found*		
				C	H	N	C	H	N
1.	Unsubstituted	> 350	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₃	73.83	4.39	12.33	73.67	4.22	12.31
2.	8-methyl	305	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₃	74.79	5.15	11.38	74.68	4.91	11.28
3.	6-chloro	> 350	C ₂₁ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₃ Cl ₂	61.45	3.17	10.24	61.29	2.82	10.57
4.	6-bromo	> 350	C ₂₁ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₃ Br ₂	50.50	2.60	8.41	50.23	2.45	8.71

* Analysed after heating in vacuum at 110° for 4 hours.

1,2-Bis(2-chloro-4-quinolyl)ethane derivatives: 1-Cyano-1,2-bis(2-chloro-4-quinolyl) ethane (IIb) derivative (1 g.) was treated with 70% sulphuric acid (10 ml.) and heated on a sand bath for 6 hrs. On pouring the reaction mixture over ice water the product (table IV) which separated crystallised from either benzene or xylene. Yield 40–45%.

TABLE IV

1,2-bis(2-chloro-4-quinolyl)ethane derivatives

No.	Substituent in 1,2-bis(2-chloro- 4-quinolyl)ethane	M.P. °C	Molecular formula	Analysis %					
				required			found		
				C	H	N	C	H	N
1.	Unsubstituted	219	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₂ Cl ₂	67.98	3.96	7.93	67.63	3.62	8.05
2.	8-methyl	225	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ N ₂ Cl ₂	69.30	4.72	7.35	69.23	4.33	7.49
3.	6-chloro	302	C ₂₀ H ₁₂ N ₂ Cl ₄	56.87	2.84	6.63	56.47	2.76	6.42
4.	6-bromo	298	C ₂₀ H ₁₂ N ₂ Cl ₂ Br ₂	46.96	2.34	5.48	46.87	2.68	5.49

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